

Effects of Photoperiod and Light Spectrum on Growth, Pigment Composition and Toxicity of Selected *Anabaena* Strains

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DOI:

Abstract: Light plays a critical role in the growth and metabolism of cyanobacteria, influencing photosynthesis, nutrient uptake and synthesis of bioactive secondary metabolites. Although light intensity and spectral quality are known to modulate cyanobacterial growth and toxin production rates, the combined effects of photoperiod and spectral composition remain insufficiently explored. This study examined how variations in light regime, photoperiod and spectral quality, affect growth, pigment composition, and toxicity in the selected *Anabaena* strains Č2 and Č5. Cultures were exposed to red and green light for 35 days at two daily illumination durations (5 h and 10 h). Chlorophyll a and phycobiliproteins (phycoerythrin, phycocyanin, and allophycocyanin) were quantified spectrophotometrically at six time points during cultivation (0, 7, 14, 21, 28, 35 days). Under red light, strain Č2 showed higher biomass and phycocyanin accumulation under 5 h exposure, while Č5 reached similar pigment levels by day 35. Green light induced lower overall pigment yields but exhibited a gradual increase in phycocyanin and allophycocyanin toward days 28–35, with both strains showing higher concentrations under prolonged illumination. The effect of photoperiod on toxicity was further evaluated under white fluorescent light (8:16, 12:12, and 16:8 h light:dark) using the *Artemia salina* bioassay. Greater toxicity was observed under prolonged illumination, peaking at 16:8 h, suggesting that extended light exposure may enhance the synthesis or release of toxic metabolites through sustained metabolic activity. These results suggest that light regime can alter cyanobacterial metabolism and toxicity, highlighting its environmental relevance under changing illumination conditions.

Keywords: cyanobacteria, photoperiod, toxicity, phycobiliproteins.

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